

DIFFERENT WAYS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

Tashkhodjayeva Patima Bakiyevna

Senior teacher of “Department of Pedagogy,
psychology
and languages” in Tashkent Medical Academy

Annotation: English is so global language. The active exposure of an ESL (English as a second language) learner to language content during the early years of language acquisition by an English language teacher promotes the learning of a second or foreign language. The ESL programs designed for young learners, usually referring to school-aged kids less than 12 years, help these non-native speakers of English to become comfortable with language use. This is demonstrated through reading comprehension, spoken fluency, and effective writing. The use of practical examples and real-life situations to teach the English language at the primary level makes it usable to students and makes language learning enjoyable. Teaching the second language by incorporating role-plays, songs and worksheets contribute to implicit learning. The use of props, photographs, illustrations, and other real-life contexts enhances acquisition and the students understand better by acting out and by keeping language input simple.

Keywords: ESL, second language teaching, Activity-based learning, English language teaching.

Аннотация: Английский язык – настолько глобальный язык. Активное знакомство учащегося ESL (английский как второй язык) с языковым содержанием в первые годы изучения языка учителем английского языка способствует изучению второго или иностранного языка. Программы ESL, разработанные для юных учащихся, обычно рассчитанные на детей школьного возраста до 12 лет, помогают этим людям, для которых английский язык не является родным, освоиться с языком. Это демонстрируется через понимание

прочитанного, беглость разговорной речи и эффективное письмо. Использование практических примеров и ситуаций из реальной жизни при обучении английскому языку на начальном уровне делает его полезным для учащихся и делает изучение языка приятным. Обучение второму языку посредством ролевых игр, песен и рабочих листов способствует имплицитному обучению. Использование реквизита, фотографий, иллюстраций и других контекстов из реальной жизни улучшает усвоение материала, и учащиеся лучше понимают, разыгрывая и сохраняя простой языковой ввод.

Ключевые слова: ESL, обучение второму языку, обучение на основе деятельности, обучение английскому языку.

English as a second or foreign language implies learning and use of the English language by speakers who are non-native speakers of this language. Second language acquisition (SLA) is a conscious process of learning another language other than the First Language (L1) of the learner. The First Language (L1) refers to the language the child is exposed to and learns from birth. It is generally the language of the parents or caregivers, and it is possible to have more than one L1. The Second Language (L2) refers to the language learned after L1 has been acquired. The teaching of English as a second language (TESL) or as a foreign language (TEFL) refers to teaching the English language to students whose mother tongue is not English. These students have different first languages/native languages. An ESL learner implies that this English language learner has already learned and acquired another language, generally the native language, before learning English. The contrastive analysis hypothesis of second language learning formulated by Robert Lado in 'Linguistics Across Cultures' assumes that the proportion of difficulties that learners will face in the study of English as a second language is determined directly by the degree to which their native language differs from English. In this book, Lado claimed that "those elements which are similar to [the learner's] native language will be simple for him, and those elements that are different will be difficult" (Lado,

1957). The influence of the L1 cannot be negated during the acquisition of L2. The L1 transfer or what is commonly called 'language interference' leads to errors in the acquisition of a second language. This necessitates the use of teaching strategies and learning techniques to address each language skill.

Young children learn mainly by 'doing' rather than by conscious learning because they learn more implicitly than older children. While many things are learned using conscious or explicit processing, a great deal is also learned implicitly or without conscious awareness (Reber, 1989). This requires abundant input and rich interaction in the target language. The best way is to incorporate playlike activities; songs, videos, props, and other fun and interactive elements to keep the students engaged. The acquisition of language by taking part in an activity shared with an adult is comparably easier than rote learning of language vocabulary and patterns. Also, the informal and playful manner of language exposure makes acquisition enjoyable, for the child is not stressed by having to achieve set standards. No sooner the child realises that proficiency targets need to be met than their motivation wanes. Therefore, a fine balance has to be achieved to foster an enduring enthusiasm for language learning and support for gaining progressive and gradual linguistic proficiency at the same time. The ESL teacher must focus on everyday interaction in the target language as constant exposure and practice from early on is the best chance of becoming fluent in the second language. Language develops best through interaction, therefore, conversations with other students in the second language and also, regular opportunities for direct contact with native target language speakers, particularly those of their age, are highly motivating.

EFFECTUAL TESL STRATEGIES FOR YOUNG MINDS

- ESL and Bilingual methods of teaching children It implies the use of both, English as well as the learner's native language as a medium of instruction. The ESL teacher can incorporate varied techniques in accordance with the requirements of the target group. The educational materials; oral lectures and written assignments can be provided in a blended mode, here the ESL teacher uses both, English and the

student's native language simultaneously for instruction and explanation. However, an alternative approach to bilingual teaching strategy advocates the use of English for all lessons while incorporating the learner's native language translation of vocabulary, grammar, and situational hints to improve language comprehension (Wright, 2010)

- Keep the energy moving; Total Physical Response (TRP) Teaching young learners can often be a challenge, to keep their interest alive and harness the attention span, keep things moving. That's where 'Total Physical Response' comes into play. In a language classroom, this teaching method requires the students to use their bodies in response to foreign language instruction. An ESL teacher can use TPR by sharing action-focused sentences with language class and demonstrate what they mean. Then have students repeat the same. Have the learners walk around and associate body movements with the language structures that are being taught. The teacher instructs in the target language and the student acts. Not only will the students start to build vocabulary associations naturally, TPR is also a tested formula to fight boredom!

- Give me your ear; listening to music in L2 Spoken language comes naturally before reading and writing. The learner needs to know the 26 letters and frequently hear the 44 sounds used in Standard English. Just hearing the target language can help children get an ear for different tones. An effective TESL strategy to teach young learners a foreign language is by listening to music in a second language, playing the song in the background constantly during language teaching will eventually have the child humming and singing the words while performing other language tasks. Music stimulates the senses and promotes language, coordination, interest, and memory. Particularly, songs that appease the young minds should be chosen and played.

- Learning by Looking; visual L2 Teaching Materials Learning a second language requires adequate exposure to the target language and resources that facilitate L2 acquisition. Screen time can be used effectively by making the child

watch TV programs; even cartoons for early learners, in English. The age-appropriate short videos contain great visual and auditory content to expose children to another language. The social streaming platform, Netflix has many TV shows for children with the possibility of adding subtitles and swapping languages. For primary level learners, some cartoons like ‘Dora the Explorer’ have been specifically designed to help children learn a foreign language. In these types of shows, children are encouraged to talk back to the cartoons. This concept is followed in other interactive educational cartoons and it helps children improve their listening and pronunciation skills.

As a result, Second language teaching needs to be incorporated in the learner’s curriculum from the early years to minimize first language interference errors. Teaching children requires activity and engagement which can be successfully achieved by using ingenious strategies that motivate practical use of the second language. In an effective ESL classroom for young learners, there should be ample language exposure, a lot of movement, repetition of language concepts, and classroom activities that are much like play! The ESL teacher thrives on props, games, and other action-oriented techniques that maximize exposure to the target language in a fun and friendly manner. The language teacher must focus on the creation of an enjoyable atmosphere conducive to learning and devise ways for the learner to practice what they have learned.

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